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EFFECTS OF MULTIPOINT LOADING OF SANDWICH PANELS AT BENDING

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SUMMARY: The simple estimates of transverse stresses in the midlayer of a sandwich panel at squeezing from the infinite system of ribs located on either face surface have been deduced. For the discrete model of a symmetric structure panel, considered in this work, the transverse normal stress at a soft midlayer is estimated proportionally with the difference in deflections of panel face layers, i.e. depends on a symmetric solution part. The way of obtaining of the results taking into account a three-point loading on an infinite strip enables the convolution operation of the solution to be carried by a superposition method for infinite set of forces. The Laplace operational method enables the solution to be derived in a closed form and makes its expansion into a series unnecessary.

Parametric analysis as applied to the cases of bilateral symmetric and asymmetric disposition of point forces with respect to a middle plane ostended the transverse normal stresses with alternating signs in the interval between the forces.

At the sections under point forces the compressive transverse stress has to do with extremum as the face layer thickness is variable. In the cases of small spans the correction factor is derived permitting to use the stress from two symmetric forces for the case of infinite set of point forces. The relationships for squeezing behavior of an infinite sandwich strip based on the applied discrete model serve as a proximate approach that is applicable to the different designs.

KEYWORDS: Sandwich Structures, Infinite Strip, Point Forces, Bending, Transversal Stresses, Local Effects.

INTRODUCTION

The engineering methods of design for the layered structures of composite materials are incessantly enriched at the expense of the results of problem solutions in applied theory that is ascribable to wide distribution of physical hypotheses and kinematic models. Contrary to the easily examined solutions for a thin-walled homogeneous structure, those are extensively applied in textbook examples [1], the solutions for laminated structures are mainly represented in the form of curves and numerical tables as the results of numerical realization of the algorithm corresponding to the discrete or global model of a plate or shell [2].

The analytical solution variant of the boundary-value problem of the elasticity theory for a finite domain is of practical importance in the analysis of local effects close to the boundaries of a structure and at the sites of the application of discontinuous load. The solution of this kind, that is reasonably simple in analysis without recourse to a specific approximation of the transverse stresses and in the case of an incompressible normal, was deduced by Vasil'ev [3] exclusively for a cantilever orthotropic beam.

SPECIFIC CHARACTER OF THE TERMINAL-DECISION FUNCTIONS FOR LOCAL EFFECTS

With the engineering bending theory, admitting variable kinematic hypotheses and thus simplifying the set of differential equations, the boundary effects are investigated by the boundary functions, damping along with their derivatives at the infinite length of a structure. With a finite structure extent the analysis of the solution and its convergence for discontinuous surface loads and point forces shows up to be complex. This seems to be the case in spite of the employment of well-developed technique where the solution is representable by the Fourier-series expansion or the series of special functions.

Proper notice must be made for the distinction of the discrete model stated in the calculation of a transverse normal stress σ_z in the infinite strip, loaded by a periodic system of point forces, as is further shown in the work. The solution for the individual element lengthwise of an infinite strip, obtained by the discrete model of three-point bending, is essentially simpler, as compared with a panel of a finite length. Under the Laplace operational method the solution is derived in a closed form [4] to render the series expansion unnecessary for the solution procedure.

ESTIMATES OF MIDLAYER SQUEEZING STRESSES OF A SANDWICH STRIP ARISING FROM MULTIPOINT TRANSVERSE FORCES

The advantages of the simple solution for an infinite strip next by a superposition method enables the convolution operation of the solution to be carried for infinite set of forces. The problem is principally solvable at the great distances among the forces, and the results of its solution in conformity to the symmetric loading are widely known [5]. For the phase shift of the system of forces on the upper face surface of a sandwich panel with respect to the system of forces on its lower surface, see Fig. 1a, the skew - symmetric deflection component has a nonzero value and hence we must invoke the problem solution of bending from three point system of forces at intervals $2l_1$ as a summation element in the superposition method.

Figure 1: Multipoint distribution of point forces along an infinite sandwich strip:
a - relative shift of the forces, **b** – unified loading, **c** - symmetric forces.

INPUT FORMULAS

The basic element of problem solution for the bending of an infinite strip type of sandwich from the self-balanced infinite system of point forces, distributed on its face surfaces, is the solution deduced in [4] for three-point loading of the strip at the loaded span equal to $2l_1$. The key parameters in evaluation of the transverse normal stress at a soft midlayer of an infinite sandwich strip are:

$$\mathbf{a} = \left[\frac{6E_z(1-\mathbf{n}_1^2)}{E_x(1-\mathbf{m})\mathbf{m}^3} \right]^{1/4}, \quad \mathbf{m} = \frac{h_1}{h_1 + h_0}$$

$$\mathbf{k}_a = \frac{1}{4\mathbf{a}} \left[1 + e^{-\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1} (\cos \mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1 - \sin \mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1) \right], \quad \mathbf{x}_1 = \frac{l_1}{h_1 + h_0}$$

$$\hat{w}_\Delta = \frac{1}{4\mathbf{a}^3} \left[1 + e^{-\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1} (\cos \mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1 + \sin \mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1) \right] \quad (1)$$

here E_x, E_z the elasticity moduli in the longitudinal direction of a face layer and in the transverse direction of a midlayer respectively, \mathbf{n}_1 the Poisson ratio of a face layer. We shall restrict our consideration to the section of infinite strip within the range $0 \leq x \leq l_1$ and the following expression of transverse stress in the indicated interval of an infinite strip can be deduced by [4]:

$$\hat{s}_z(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{q_0 E_z}{1-\mathbf{m}} \frac{1}{4\mathbf{a}^3} \left\{ e^{-\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}} (\cos \mathbf{a}\mathbf{x} + \sin \mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}) \right.$$

$$+ \frac{e^{-\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x})}}{2} [\cos \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}) + \sin \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x})] +$$

$$\left. + \frac{e^{-\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x})}}{2} [\cos \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x}) + \sin \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x})] \right\} \quad (2)$$

where $0 \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_1$, $\mathbf{x} = \frac{x}{h_1 + h_0}$, $q_0 = \frac{6P(1-\mathbf{n}_1^2)}{b(h_1 + h_0)E_x\mathbf{m}^3}$, b – band width.

Beyond the limit of the interval $\mathbf{x} > \mathbf{x}_1$ the expression (2) should be supplemented by the additional summand accounted for in the general notation [4]. Point supports $P/2$ applied to the infinite strip are automatically considered in the solution for every system of three-point loading and therefore these forces are shown in Fig. 1b by the dashed arrows.

To make use of the superposition method, that allows us to sum up the effect of finite number of equally spaced point forces, see Fig. 1b, on stress value $\hat{s}_z(\mathbf{x})$ in the above-mentioned interval, it is necessary to include into calculation by the generalized formula from [4] the summands in $\mathbf{x} > (2m-1)\mathbf{x}_1$ when $m = \overline{1, N}$. The proper indication refers in this case to the extreme points of a total loading section. The last point forces applied solely to the one face surface are equal to $P/2$ because of these forces combined with the rest forces applied to two surfaces, each of them equals P , are self-balanced provided that the grouped moment equal to zero. As a result for transversal stress on the interval $0 \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_1$ the following expression can be got:

$$\begin{aligned}
s_z(\mathbf{x}) = \hat{s}_z(\mathbf{x}) + \sum_{m=1}^N \left\{ -\hat{w}_\Delta \operatorname{cha}(2m\mathbf{x}_1 \mu \mathbf{x}) \operatorname{cosa}(2m\mathbf{x}_1 \mu \mathbf{x}) + \right. \\
\left. + \frac{k_a}{a^2} \operatorname{sha}(2m\mathbf{x}_1 \mu \mathbf{x}) \operatorname{sina}(2m\mathbf{x}_1 \mu \mathbf{x}) + \right. \\
+ \frac{1}{4a^3} [\operatorname{sha}(2m\mathbf{x}_1 \mu \mathbf{x}) \operatorname{cosa}(2m\mathbf{x}_1 \mu \mathbf{x}) - \operatorname{cha}(2m\mathbf{x}_1 \mu \mathbf{x}) \operatorname{sina}(2m\mathbf{x}_1 \mu \mathbf{x})] + \\
+ \frac{1}{4a^3} [\operatorname{sha}((2m-1)\mathbf{x}_1 \mu \mathbf{x}) \operatorname{cosa}((2m-1)\mathbf{x}_1 \mu \mathbf{x}) - \\
\left. - \operatorname{cha}((2m-1)\mathbf{x}_1 \mu \mathbf{x}) \operatorname{sina}((2m-1)\mathbf{x}_1 \mu \mathbf{x})] \right\} \quad (3)
\end{aligned}$$

A prime at the sign of a sum denotes, that the summation is carried on with respect to every all summands: first at $-\mathbf{x}$ next at $+\mathbf{x}$. These summands depend on the distance of every cell of three-point loading scheme to the section AA' . Fall of a longitudinal coordinate outside the limits of the every three-point loading cell ($x > l_1$) is taken into account in eqn (3) by means of additional summands $2m\mathbf{x}_1$ and $(2m-1)\mathbf{x}_1$ to an argument of corresponding functions as the origin of the local frame of reference for the individual scheme of three-point bending falls on the line of a force action P .

UNIFIED LOADING BY THE UNLIMITED ROW OF POINT FORCES

Manipulation of infinite sum in the expression (3), ad hoc $N \rightarrow \infty$, was performed with a view to isolate the summands in the form of the products of exponential with positive and negative exponents into trigonometric functions of a monomial argument. It is easy to verify, that the summands with positive exponents can be reduced and we resorted to the following known limits:

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} e^{-tm} \sin mx = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sin x}{ch t - \cos x}, \quad 1 + 2 \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} e^{-tm} \cos mx = \frac{sh t}{ch t - \cos x}, \quad (t > 0) \quad (4)$$

to yield the limiting expressions of an infinite sum, which summands should be expressed in terms of the products of the exponential with a negative exponent by the sine/cosine of the argument proportional to the positive integers. The following limiting expression of transverse stresses in squeezing of a panel by dint of the chart in the Fig. 1b can be deduced as a result, substituting the parameters k_a and \hat{w}_Δ from eqns (1) in eqn (3) and considering eqn (2):

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{s}_z^{(b)}(\mathbf{x}) = & \hat{\mathbf{s}}_z(\mathbf{x}) - \hat{\mathbf{s}}_z^0 \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{sh\,2\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1 + \sin\,2\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1}{ch\,2\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1 - \cos\,2\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1} \right) \left[ch\,\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x} \cos\,\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x} + \right. \right. \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \left(ch\,\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}) \cos\,\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}) + ch\,\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x}) \cos\,\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x}) \right) \left. \right] - \\
& - \left(1 - \frac{sh\,2\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1 - \sin\,2\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1}{ch\,2\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1 - \cos\,2\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}_1} \right) \left[sha\,\mathbf{x} \sin\,\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x} + \right. \\
& \left. \left. + \frac{1}{2} \left(sha(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}) \sin\,\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}) + sha(\mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x}) \sin\,\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}_1 + \mathbf{x}) \right) \right] \right\}, \quad 0 \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_1
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Here the following designation is introduced for the transverse normal stress at the center of a sandwich panel loaded by a three-point scheme with a big span, i. e. evaluated from eqn (2) at $\mathbf{x}_1 \gg 1$:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}_z^0 = \hat{\mathbf{s}}_z(0) = -\frac{q_0 E_z}{1 - m} \cdot \frac{1}{4a^3} = -\frac{Pa}{4b(h_1 + h_0)} \tag{6}$$

This stress is also in agreement with the transverse stress in squeezing of an infinite panel by two contrarily directed forces $P/2$ in magnitude.

LOADING BY SYMMETRIC POINT FORCES

For the loading of sandwich strip by the infinite system of equal and opposite forces when the upper force is locked into step with the lower one, Fig. 1c, the formal change of indices in eqn (3)

is useful and the parameters $\mathbf{k}_a, \hat{w}_\Delta$ together with the function $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_z(\mathbf{x})$ should be also altered. The doubled values of all terms under the summation sign with even-numbered summation counter $2m$ can be obtained as a result, taken for this case the relative half-span value $\mathbf{x}_1 = 0$ in eqns (1)

and the values $\hat{w}_\Delta = \mathbf{k}_a / \mathbf{a}^2 = 1/2\mathbf{a}^3$ deduced in eqn (3). Notice that odd-numbered summation counter $(2m-1)$ in the last group of terms in eqn (3) also becomes even-numbered $2m$ as the span length in the model of a three-point loading, which stands duty as a separate loading element, is taken to be zero. For this reason the relationship from eqn (2) should be supplemented

by the additional group of terms $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_z^0 (ch\,\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x} \sin\,\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x} - sh\,\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x} \cos\,\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x})$, see [4], as the interval $0 \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_1$ is beyond the limits of a trivial section where a loading by two equal and opposite forces occurs, per se the origin pertains to the section AA'. The following formula can be obtained instead of eqn (2) as a result for $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_z$ in a strip loaded by two forces:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}_z(\mathbf{x}) = 2\hat{\mathbf{s}}_z^0 e^{-\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}} (\cos\,\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x} + \sin\,\mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}) \tag{7}$$

On application the indicated manipulation to the eqn (3) for the loading of a sandwich strip shown in Fig. 1c, the limit representation of the stress $\mathbf{s}_z(\mathbf{x})$ in the case of $N \rightarrow \infty$ having used the relationships (4) can be deduced as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{s}_z^{(c)}(\mathbf{x}) = 2\hat{\mathbf{s}}_z^0 \left[e^{-\mathbf{ax}}(\cos \mathbf{ax} + \sin \mathbf{ax}) - \left(1 - \frac{sh 2\mathbf{ax}_1 + \sin 2\mathbf{ax}_1}{ch 2\mathbf{ax}_1 - \cos 2\mathbf{ax}_1} \right) ch \mathbf{ax} \cos \mathbf{ax} + \right. \\ \left. + \left(1 - \frac{sh 2\mathbf{ax}_1 - \sin 2\mathbf{ax}_1}{ch 2\mathbf{ax}_1 - \cos 2\mathbf{ax}_1} \right) sh \mathbf{ax} \sin \mathbf{ax} \right], \quad 0 \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

LOADING IN ANTI-PHASE SHIFT OF POINT FORCES

For the loading in accordance with Fig. 1a we derive the formula:

$$\mathbf{s}_z^{(a)}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{s}_z^{(b)}(\mathbf{x}) - \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{s}_z^{(c)}(\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}), \quad 0 \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_1 \quad (9)$$

Second summand in eqn (9) is calculated by the eqn (8) substituting in it the difference $\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}$ instead of the variable \mathbf{x} . For the analytical notation of $\mathbf{s}_z^{(a)}(\mathbf{x})$ the only expression $\mathbf{s}_z^{(b)}(\mathbf{x})$ is formally usable on the interval $0 \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_1$ with the sign preliminary reversed in conformity to the summands, containing the difference $\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}$ as an argument.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Diagrams of midlayer transverse stresses, calculated by the discrete model adopted for the cases of multipoint loading according to the charts in Fig. 1a,b,c, displayed as curves and surfaces in Fig. 2-4. As a data-sheet value of concentrated force, constant across the width b of a sandwich strip, a force P is adopted, for which $P/bh = 1 \text{ MPa}$, ($h = 2h_1 + h_0$). Typical difference of the diagrams $\mathbf{s}_z(\mathbf{x})$ over a characteristic repeated interval for all three charts of multipoint loading, moreover the three-point loading of a strip included for comparison, is shown in Fig. 2.

The fact is, that the double differing $\mathbf{s}_z(\mathbf{x})$ shown by the curves 3;1 in Fig. 2, according to the charts *a* and *c* in Fig. 1, takes place over the entire interval $0 \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_1$. The last circumstance stems from the transverse stress dependence on a symmetric component of the solution proportional to the difference of the face layer deflections according to the model assumed. This fact is easy to verify analytically. When the eqn (8) is compared with eqn (9) it follows:

$$\mathbf{s}_z^{(a)}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{s}_z^{(c)}(\mathbf{x}), \quad 0 \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_1 \quad (10)$$

We emphasize, that for usability of the eqn (10) the interval between forces on the either side of a strip in the anti-phase shift of force sets (chart *a*) is twice as long than for the symmetric set of forces (chart *c*).

Positive transverse normal stresses arise from the oscillating functions. These stresses are liable to initiate failure in case of small strength of a filler in tension. With small steps $2l_1$ between forces the stresses $\mathbf{s}_z(\mathbf{x}) \approx const$ over all interval $0 \leq x \leq l_1$, see Fig. 3 for loading chart *c* in Fig. 1. Here a zero level line separates the black coordinate lines for $\mathbf{s}_z < 0$ from the lines with flat tints for $\mathbf{s}_z > 0$.

The compressive stress \mathbf{s}_z of a midlayer at the section AA' ($x=0$) being under force has only weak dependence on greater l_1 ceteris paribus, however with small l_1 it increases steeply, see Fig. 4. This stress is obtained from the formula (8):

$$s_z^{(c)}(0) = -\frac{Pa}{2b(h_1 + h_0)} \cdot \frac{sh2ax_1 + \sin 2ax_1}{ch2ax_1 - \cos 2ax_1} \quad (11)$$

The level line in Fig. 4 separates the black coordinate lines for $-s_z^{(c)} > 1$ from the lines with flat tints for $-s_z^{(c)} < 1$. Input specifications are the same, as in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Transverse normal stresses in a filler: 1 – refers to the loading in Fig. 1c; 2 – $1b$; 3 – $1a$; 4 - three-point loading of an infinite strip.
 $l_1/h=3$, $h_0 = 2h_1 = 0.006m$, $E_x = 40GPà$, $E_z = 0.310GPà$.

Figure 3: Diagram of transverse stresses over the repeating interval versus its relative length. Input specifications are the same, as in Fig. 2.

Figure 4: Effect of the relative volumetric contents of face layers $m = 2h_1 / h$ on the midlayer squeezing stresses at the maximally loaded section AA' ($x = 0$).

CONCLUSIONS

The derivation of formulae for midlayer squeezing stresses in an infinite strip of symmetric sandwich type and their parametric analysis as applied to the cases of the symmetric and shifted disposition of point forces with respect to a middle plane has shown:

- Transverse stresses from the infinite set of anti-phase shifted point forces equally spaced along an either face surface may be calculated up to the factor 1/2 by the simpler formulae for the symmetric set of forces spaced at intervals less by half than for the shifted set.
- A compressive stress $s_z(0)$ being at the sections under point forces is increased several times as the face layer thickness is reduced within the limits $0.35 \geq 2h_1 / h \geq 0.05$. In the cases of small spans and the least ratio $E_z / E_x^{(1)}$ the correction factor is derived permitting the calculated value $s_z(0)$ from two forces to utilize for the case of infinite set of point forces.
- Concerning the intermediate section of an interval between forces there the oscillatory solution components promote at certain parameters the appearance of the stresses of reversed sign. In the case of sandwich elastic constants typical of HEXCEL/Al the effect indicated makes itself evident in small face layer thickness, with a filler stiffness by the order of magnitude greater and at small intervals between forces. A tenfold decrease occurs to the positive value of $s_z(x_1)$ as the face layer thickness and/or the interval between forces increases twice-thrice. The compressive stress $s_z(x_1)$ shows the greatest and stable values with the face layer thickness enlarged as well as the filler stiffness and the intervals between forces essentially reduced.

The expressions derived, diagrams and illustrations of parametric analysis of transverse filler stresses may be useful in the express estimate of squeezing behavior in different designs of sandwich panels loaded by periodic set of point forces.

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